

THE ROLE OF A COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH IN DEVELOPING THE SKILL OF EVALUATING LITERARY CHARACTERS AND ITS IMPACT ON FORMING NATIONAL IDENTITY

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Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются теоретико-методические основы компетентностного подхода в развитии навыков оценки героев литературных произведений. Рассматриваются возможности развития у учащихся нравственных, эстетических, коммуникативных и творческих компетенций в процессе анализа и оценки персонажей художественных произведений. Также описана методическая модель образовательного процесса, организованного на основе компетентностного подхода, его структурные компоненты и педагогическая эффективность. Исследование обосновывает значение процесса оценки героев произведений в формировании национальной идентичности учащихся, понимании национальных ценностей и воспитании уважения к ним. В результате освещена роль компетентностного подхода как личностно-ориентированной, интегративной и инновационной педагогической технологии в литературном образовании.

Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of the competency-based approach in developing skills for evaluating the characters of literary works. The possibilities of developing students' moral, aesthetic, communicative, and creative competencies in the process of analyzing and evaluating characters in literary works are considered. The methodological model of the educational process organized on the basis of a competency-based approach, its structural components, and pedagogical effectiveness are also described. The study substantiates the importance of the process of evaluating the heroes of the works in forming the national identity of students, understanding national values and fostering respect for them. As a result, the role of the competency-based approach as a person-oriented, integrative and innovative pedagogical technology in literary education is highlighted.

Ключевые слова: компетентностный подход, литературное образование, герой произведения, навык оценки, национальная идентичность, национальные ценности, художественный анализ, критическое мышление, рефлексивное мышление, коммуникативная компетентность, нравственная компетентность, эстетическое воспитание.

Keywords: competency-based approach, literary education, hero of the work, assessment skills, national identity, national values, artistic analysis, critical thinking, reflexive thinking, communicative competence, moral competence, aesthetic education.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke about a number of issues, in particular, he said: "To increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but all members of our society, first of all, science and enlightenment, high spirituality are needed. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance, and, of course, error from the right path. As Eastern sages said, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and

knowledge, the greatest heritage is good upbringing, and the greatest poverty is ignorance"¹.

Today, the reforms being implemented in the education system, new approaches, and the introduction of competency-based paradigms provide for the comprehensive development of the student's personality, the formation of their thinking, aesthetic, and moral views, as well as increasing the effectiveness of the process of preparation for life. In this sense, the issue of developing the ability to evaluate the characters of a work is of particular scientific importance as one of the central directions of modern literary education.

In modern pedagogical theory, the competency-based approach is regarded as a new criterion for assessing the quality of education. It is a system aimed at forming the ability of the student's personality not only to acquire knowledge but also to apply this knowledge in practice, independently analyze, engage in communication, think creatively, and use it in solving life problems. Thus, the educational process organized on the basis of a competency-based approach forms the student not as a student who memorizes ready-made knowledge, but as an active subject who searches for, analyzes, and evaluates knowledge. As a methodological model, this process includes several important components: target, content, activity, evaluation, and result components. The target component involves developing students' national identity competence alongside moral, aesthetic, and intellectual competencies by understanding the characters of a work of art and evaluating their personality, motives, and behavior. The content component is aimed at deepening the analysis of the work, revealing the character of the characters, their mental state, the author's position and the inner essence of the images created through artistic means, as well as understanding the national values, customs, traditions and features of the national character reflected in them. The activity component involves students in the active learning process through interactive games, problem-based questions, analytical conversations, discussions, and role-playing scenes, encouraging them to evaluate the characters' actions from the perspective of national and universal values.

The evaluation component serves to determine the level of students' analytical thinking, culture of argumentation, independent position, artistic and aesthetic thinking, as well as the understanding and attitude toward national values. The resulting component determines the student's personal attitude toward the characters, moral views, creative thinking, artistic and aesthetic taste, the level of national self-awareness, and indicators of self-identification as a person. The effectiveness of this model is ensured by activating the student's learning activity, encouraging them to think, ask questions, and argue. At the same time, the essence of the teacher's activity changes: he becomes a person who does not provide information, but rather directs, manages analysis, and stimulates the students' thinking process.

The process of developing the ability to evaluate the characters of a work based on a competency-based approach is an important means of forming and strengthening national identity in students. This is because the historical memory, national values, customs, traditions, and spiritual ideals of the people are embodied in the characters of works of art. In the process of analyzing the characters' actions, life positions, and moral choices, the student evaluates them based on the criteria of national and universal human values. As a result, a conscious attitude toward the cultural heritage, spiritual wealth, and national character of one's people is formed within them.

Discussions, role-playing games, and problem situations organized within the activity component allow students to understand the vital significance of national values, express a personal

¹ <https://www.norma.uz>. 2020-yil 24-yanvar kuni Prezident Shavkat Mirziyoyev O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisiga joriy yil va kelgusidagi mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotining eng ustuvor vazifalari to'g'risida Murojaatnomasi.

attitude toward them, and justify their position. This increases the level of students' national self-awareness and develops their sense of civic responsibility and national pride. Through the evaluative and resulting components, the level of students' ability to analyze characters, understand national values, express an attitude toward them, and form their own personal views is determined. Thus, the development of the ability to evaluate the characters of a work based on a competency-based approach serves to form not only literary-analytical, moral, and communicative competencies but also the competence of national identity. As a result, the student understands their national identity, values national values, and harmonizes them with modern life.

A methodological model formed on the basis of a competency-based approach develops a number of important competencies in students. First, moral competence involves evaluating the actions of characters based on human values and moral norms. Secondly, creative competence forms the ability to interpret the events of a work differently, find alternative solutions, and put forward one's own point of view. Third, communicative competence develops the skills of expressing one's thoughts clearly and logically, participating in discussions, listening to the opinions of others, and treating them with respect. Fourth, cultural-aesthetic competence allows for the understanding of the aesthetic beauty of a work of art, the system of images, the richness of language, and literary values.

From a practical perspective, the methodological model for developing the ability to evaluate the characters of a work based on a competency-based approach includes a number of interactive and innovative strategies in the educational process.

As the first practical step, students are given the task of deeply studying the text of the work and determining the character, mental state, and social position of the characters.

In the second practical stage, students are taught to evaluate the characters' actions from various perspectives. Role-playing games and discussion methods play a central role in this process. For example, students perform a scene in the role of a character and defend or criticize their decisions. In this way, the student has the opportunity to argue their opinion, listen to the opinions of others and analyze them. During the discussion process, students interpret and evaluate the actions of a single character differently, which develops creative thinking and a reflexive approach.

To increase the effectiveness of the methodological model in the educational process, the teacher creates problem situations. For example, by discussing the character's moral dilemma, the reader analyzes events, identifies the reasons for decisions, and evaluates them based on moral and aesthetic criteria.

In conclusion, the methodological model of the educational process, organized on the basis of a competency-based approach to developing the skills of evaluating the characters of a work, serves to develop not only the literary knowledge of students, but also their moral, aesthetic, communicative and social competencies. In particular, in the process of evaluating characters, students rely on spiritual criteria related to national values, historical and cultural heritage, customs, and traditions. This serves to foster a sense of national identity, national pride, and national belonging among them. National character, patriotism, humanism, diligence, family spirit, and meaning reflected in works of art.

From this perspective, developing the ability to evaluate the characters of a work based on a competency-based approach is an effective pedagogical tool not only for forming literary-analytical competencies but also for strengthening the national identity of students. As a result, it will be

possible to raise a harmoniously developed person who understands their national values, treats them with respect, is able to think critically and creatively, and has an active civic position. Consequently, this methodological model is of great scientific and practical importance as an innovative system of modern literary education aimed at the individual and serving the development of national values.

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